

D3.3: Final version of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan

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Work Package	Work Package 3
Task	T3.1 Development of the knowledge sharing methodology
Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	21/12/2023
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Version	3.0
Dissemination Level	Public
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.10391616

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
0.1	13/06/2021	First Draft	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)
0.2	22/06/2021	Comments from partner integrated	Eugenia Vilarchao (ESF), Gitte Kragh (AU), Matteo Di Rosa (APRE), Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE)
1.0	25/06/2021	Final version submitted	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)
1.1	19/08/2022	Update of the first version of the plan (D3.1)	Claudia Iasillo (APRE), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)
1.2	26/08/2022	Comments from partner integrated	Eugenia Vilarchao (ESF), Maria Rosa Mondardini (UZH)
2.0	28/08/2022	Version submitted	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)
2.1	14/12/2023	Update of the second version of the plan (D3.2)	Claudia Iasillo (APRE), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)
2.2	20/12/2023	Comments from partner integrated	Asya Salnikova (ESF), Gitte Kragh (AU)
3.0	21/12/2023	Version submitted	Claudia Iasillo (APRE), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)

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List of Abbreviations

AU	Aarhus University
CS	Citizen Science
CC-CS	Citizen Science Center Zurich
DoA	Description of Action
IA	Intervention Area
FR	Front-Runner
GA	Grounding Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
OS	Open Science
PES	Public Engagement in Science
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
UCL	University College London
UZH	University of Zurich
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The following document is the update of the second version of the TIME4CS Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan (D3.2). The plan was meant as a guide for TIME4CS partners in the organization of the activities foreseen in the Knowledge sharing and Mutual learning programme between Front-Runners and Implementers (WP3) as well as in the co-designing and updating of the Implementers' roadmaps with their local stakeholders (WP2).

The plan describes the **framework of mutual learning and knowledge exchange** designed to support the implementation and the evaluation of the Grounding Actions carried out during TIME4CS lifetime, leading to long-term Institutional Changes in the implementers' institution with the ultimate goal to encourage Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology.

The first versions of the document defined the approach, contents and type of activities of the mutual learning process to be developed throughout the TIME4CS project and it shaped the Knowledge Transfer from Front-Runners to Implementers (T3.2) and the Mentoring Programme (T3.3). The types, scope, workplan, schedule, and reporting system of the events were all described in the document, that was updated at M18 (June 2022). The current document is the final update of the plan to include the adjustments to the Knowledge sharing programme depending on the Implementers roadmaps implementation in the second half of the project and their learning needs in the interaction with Front-Runners. This update provides a final overview of all the mutual learning activities carried out and more insights on the outcomes and effectiveness of the mutual learning and knowledge exchange between Implementers and Front-Runners.

1. Overview of the project

TIME4CS – Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology – is an H2020 project funded under the Science with and for Society Work Programme in the call SwafS-23-2020 “Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science”.

The project aims at **supporting and facilitating the implementation of sustainable Institutional Changes in Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)** to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology. To achieve its overall aim, TIME4CS has identified 4 **Intervention Areas (IAs)** that alone or combined can stimulate the Institutional Changes necessary to promote Citizen Science in Research and Innovation processes: 1) *Research*, 2) *Education and Awareness*, 3) *Support resources and Infrastructure* and 4) *Policy and Assessment*. TIME4CS analyzes these areas to consolidate the knowledge about the institutional adoption, establishment and maintenance of Citizen Science capacity and to establish a model for Citizen Science expansion through Institutional Changes.

For each Intervention Area, TIME4CS has identified an organization that has already undergone some Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science showing therefore a comprehensive knowledge and expertise on the matter. The knowledge of these partners, called **Front-Runners (FRs)**, contributes to the definition of a set of practical actions aimed at paving the way to Institutional Changes, defined as **Grounding Actions (GAs)**. FRs interact with and mentor four organizations willing to face the challenge of introducing Citizen Science more and more in their structures. These organizations, defined as **Implementers (Is)**, within TIME4CS lifetime develop tailored roadmaps including a specific set of Grounding Actions to carry out, benefitting from the constant support of Front-Runners. The interaction between Front-Runners and Implementers takes place during the whole TIME4CS lifetime through the development of a **Mutual Learning and Knowledge exchange** framework designed to support the implementation and the evaluation of the Grounding Actions leading to Institutional Changes, with the ultimate goal of encouraging public engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology (see [Figure 1](#)).

Figure 1 - TIME4CS methodology phases

2. Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning in the overall TIME4CS approach

2.1 Aim of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning programme

Within TIME4CS, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme was considered a learning method paramount for the achievement of the overall objective of the project, namely, to support the institutional adoption and maintenance of Citizen Science by triggering the development of sustainable Institutional Changes in the governance and in the structural organization of RPOs. In TIME4CS, knowledge exchange and mutual learning were regarded as dynamic and evolving processes depending on the different phases of the project and the needs of involved actors. Overall, the programme was aimed at facilitating the exchange of experiences and the co-creation of common solutions to similar problems, and at capitalizing on shared experiences and the set of best practices and lesson learnt collected in WP1 – Citizen Science state of the art and overcoming challenges (as described in D1.2 Best practice repository of TIME4CS Front-Runners¹, released in June 2021, and D1.3 Lesson learnt repository of TIME4CS², released in March 2022).

The knowledge exchange and mutual learning programme established between TIME4CS Front-Runners and Implementers built upon the exchange of experiences and points of view between the different organizations, and, as such, it was primarily aimed at concretely supporting the Implementers in the definition and carrying out of selected GAs, as detailed in their tailored roadmaps (developed in TIME4CS WP2 - Roadmap framework leading to institutional changes and described in D2.3 Final version of the Compilation of roadmaps and Grounding Actions for the Implementers³), benefitting from the expertise of the Front-Runners. At the same time, the exchange between Front-Runners and Implementers was beneficial also for the Front-Runners, that thanks to their mentoring role had the opportunity to learn more about needs and challenges in different environments and to gain insights into the replicability of specific actions in different contexts.

With those overall objectives established, the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning programme provided partners with practical knowledge and concrete examples and inputs for the implementation of the GAs, to capitalize on the experience of the Front-Runners and to create a common framework for the process of developing and implementing institutional roadmaps, contributing to increased knowledge on how to stimulate institutional changes thanks to the experience in TIME4CS.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017362>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6402091>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743298>

2.2 Aim of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan

WP3 aimed at providing a continuous exchange between TIME4CS Front-Runners and Implementers. Therefore, the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan overall aimed at providing the basis for the design of an **effective framework for knowledge exchange**, designed as an ongoing and evolving process that followed the Implementers and it was adjusted to respond to their new needs over time, while implementing their Grounding Actions.

This document represents the final update of the Knowledge Sharing and Mutual Learning Plan, that since its first definition at M6 (June 2021) was defining the approach, the contents and the type of activities of the mutual learning process to be developed and implemented during the TIME4CS project. The plan shaped the Knowledge Transfer from Front-Runners to Implementers (T3.2) as well as the Mentoring Programme (T3.3). The former was an opportunity for knowledge exchange in the form of workshops organized and hosted by the Front-Runners - namely virtual **learning visits** - to provide insights about their experience in the institutional adoption and maintenance of citizen science (whose outcomes are thoroughly described in D3.4: Report on TIME4CS Knowledge Transfer from Front-Runners to Implementers⁴, submitted in December 2021). The latter represented the opportunity for Implementers to host Front-Runners at their institutions during the implementation phase of their Grounding Actions to discuss possible adjustments to their actions and to establish a link with the local stakeholders, underlining the **mentoring role** of Front-Runners within TIME4CS (whose outcomes are thoroughly described in D3.5: Report on TIME4CS Mentoring Programme⁵, submitted in June 2023).

This document describes:

- the setup of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events (see Chapter 3. Setup of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events) detailing the types, the scope and the workplan of the events. The plan does not aim at providing a list of possible methods, but a common framework for the design of the internal learning activities within the project;
- the schedule of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events (see Chapter 4. Schedule of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events).
- an overview of the main outcomes and effectiveness of the programme (see Chapter 5. Conclusions).

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5805896>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8082479>

3. Setup of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events

In TIME4CS, different types of events were foreseen as part of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan, and they were integrated in the different phases of the project's methodology (see [Figure 1](#)). For the implementation of the different events, partners were advised about various aspects to be taken into consideration when designing those events in line with the specific objectives (e.g. definition of aim, expected outputs and outcomes, topic, participants, activities and assessment) in the first releases of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan.

3.1 Types of Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events in TIME4CS

In TIME4CS, three main types of Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events were planned:

1. Knowledge sharing from Front-Runners to Implementers (T3.2),
2. Mentoring Visits (T3.3),
3. Co-creation and co-designing events (T2.2).

Details of each event, including type, description, timeframe, organizer, attendees and task to which it was linked, were described in a table available to the TIME4CS consortium. The table was meant both as guideline and as an internal monitoring tool to ensure a smooth course of action during the project. The table is available in the [project shared folder](#) (for internal use of consortium members).

1. Knowledge sharing from Front-Runners to Implementers events (T3.2)

These events fell in the methodology's phases of consolidation of knowledge and in the co-designing of the Implementers' roadmaps. They took place in the first 12 months (Jan-Dec 2021) of the project, and they were aimed at:

- **gathering knowledge** from the Front-Runners for the definition of concrete Grounding Actions in each Intervention Area defining best practices and lessons learnt (T1.2) as basis for the roadmap development,
- providing Implementers with **support in the design phase of their individual roadmaps** by Front-Runners sharing their know-how and success and/or failure factors (learning visits).

During the TIME4CS proposal preparation phase, before the kick-off of the project in January 2021, the learning visits were described as a full day workshop organized by each Front-Runner in the first year of the project, with the participation of relevant teams and stakeholders of each organization depending on the Grounding Actions to be discussed for each Intervention Area. Both Implementers' project staff and members of their governance were meant to attend each learning visit. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, these face-to-

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face learning visits were instead held online via Zoom, with the support of digital collaborative tools to make the format more interactive and foster more active participation (i.e. MIRO), to ensure that there were no delays in the definition of the individual roadmaps and the following commencement of the implementing phase. The online format of the meetings allowed Implementers to invite also some of their internal stakeholders to attend the whole event, or at least to relevant sessions. Each Front-Runner organised a workshop covering one (in the case of CC-CS two) of the four Intervention Areas. The workshops' goals were to initiate a continuous support from the FRs to the Implementers throughout the duration of the project and establish privileged contacts with - and access to - the FR's know-how, before the start of the implementation of Grounding Actions (T2.3-T2.6). The three workshops focused on:

- Workshop 1: IA Education & Awareness, led by AU on Tuesday, October 19th, 2021, 12–2pm CEST
- Workshop 2: IA Research, led by UCL on Wednesday, October 27th, 2021, 12–2pm CEST
- Workshop 3: IA Support Resources & Infrastructure and IA Policy & Assessment, led by CC-CS on Wednesday, November 3rd, 2021, 12–2pm CEST

Thanks to the knowledge gathered within the activities of T1.2, T2.1 and T2.2, in the workshops the FRs were able to focus on the GAs chosen by each Implementer as part of their initial roadmaps. This helped each of them to further define the GAs and the first version of their roadmaps. The main outcomes of the workshops are described in the D3.4 Report on TIME4CS Knowledge transfer from Front-Runners to Implementers⁶.

2. Mentoring Programme (T3.3)

2a) Mentoring Visits

As of M12 of the project (December 2021), the implementing phase of TIME4CS kicked-off. To support the implementation of their Grounding Actions, Implementers benefited from a Mentoring Programme (T3.2) running until the end of the project. As part of the programme, four mentoring visits (in person) were organized, one by each Implementer, hosting the Front-Runners and whenever possible inviting a member of the TIME4CS Advisory Board when possible (T-UCC mentoring visit, specifically) and the stakeholders involved in the implementing phase. The aim of these visits was to discuss the progress and needs of the Implementers, benefitting from suggestions from Front-Runners and from their direct interaction with the local environment. The mentoring visits are described in detail in D3.5: Report on TIME4CS Mentoring Programme⁷.

2b) Implementers Journey and Implementers Forum

The mentoring programme was complemented by a series of regular online exchanges between Front-Runners and Implementers to discuss the details of the implementation of the Grounding Actions. The series consisted of quarterly meetings alternating two different formats designed to facilitate the follow-up of

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5805896>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8082479>

activities, achievements and challenges of each Implementer while also sharing experiences with other Implementers or with the Front Runners (Figure 2). The two formats of the online exchanges were:

- **Implementers Forum** – attended by representatives of all Implementer RPOs, who presented and discussed among them their progresses, challenges and opportunities for each specific GA in their roadmap, answering a pre-defined set of detailed explorative questions. The Forum was facilitated by APRE, ESF and ZSI.
- **Implementers Journeys** – these virtual meetings, one per Implementer, were attended by representatives of the specific RPO, FRs, supporting partners, and other stakeholders. Based on a reporting template (see APPENDIX B – Implementers Journey Review), each Implementer shared the process of working with the selected GAs, and got dedicated time by Front-Runners, including tailored feedback and support.

Figure 2 – Tentative schedule of the quarterly meetings in the format of “Implementers Forum” and “Implementers Journey”

For the final schedule of the mentoring visits and online exchanges refer to Chapter 4. Schedule of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events.

3. Co-creation and co-designing events (T2.2)

The Implementers’ Roadmaps developed in the frame of WP2 activities (Roadmap framework leading to institutional changes) were meant as living documents describing a detailed and tailored action plan for each Implementer defining the short-term goals (namely the Grounding Actions to be carried out during the project lifetime) that provided the basis for the medium- to long-term development process and goal (the Institutional Change). The Roadmaps detail needs, goals, obstacles, resources, previous experiences and the timeframe for each Grounding Action. The first version of the Implementers Roadmaps is available in D2.1⁸, it was updated in a second version submitted in December 2022 (D2.2)⁹, while the final version was

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743299>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7491568>

submitted in December 2023 (D2.3¹⁰). Each roadmap was meant to be co-produced with local stakeholders of the Implementers, as a result of the organization of at least three co-creation events with the actors involved in their implementation process. Each event fell under a specific phase of the TIME4CS methodology and therefore had different objectives and expected outcomes. In particular:

1. **1st co-creation meeting:** the aim of this event was the co-design of the first version of the roadmaps and the definition of Grounding Actions to include, in collaboration with the local actors that would be involved in the different actions. Goals and expectations were discussed and co-defined with local stakeholders. The meetings, held in the national language, took place in October-November 2021, before the beginning of the implementation phase. Each Implementer was responsible for the design of the format of these workshops according to its institutional context.
2. **2nd co-creation meeting:** the aim of this event was to discuss and evaluate the implementation of the Grounding Actions, after one year of activities, with local actors, representing the quadruple helix. Possible adjustments to the roadmaps were discussed, since an update of the roadmaps was foreseen for December 2022.
3. **3rd co-creation meeting:** the aim of this event was to discuss the achievements, the impacts and the sustainability of the implemented Grounding Actions and to discuss the medium- to long-term evolution of the goals of each roadmap on sustainable Institutional Changes for the implementing organizations with the support of the ecosystem of actors built during the project implementation.

For the schedule of the co-creation meetings, refer to Chapter 4. Schedule of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events.

3.2 Work plan of the events

The quality and impact of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events strongly depended on the level of preparation of each of them. Their planning took into account the specific clear aim, the desired outcomes and outputs, the topic, the participants and included the final assessment procedures. In the following sections, each of these elements is discussed, and it was used by TIME4CS partners as guidelines for the key aspects to take into consideration in the preparation of the events.

3.2.1 Define the aim and expected outputs and outcomes of each event

The aim as well as the expected outputs and outcomes of each event were considered and clearly defined at the beginning of the design phase for each event. Outputs were defined as results achieved immediately after the event (e.g. documents, reports, *etc.*), while outcomes were defined as longer-term results, such as follow-up activities. Both were indicated in the template of the event's report, which can also be used as a guideline in the design phase (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT EVENT REPORT).

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743298>

In the process of agreeing on expected outputs and outcomes of each event, the event organizer referred to the project methodology. The clear definition of the outputs and the expected outcomes of each event was essential for the next steps of the event preparation, including the definition of the guiding questions and the definition of the participants who needed to be involved in the activities.

3.2.2 Define the topic

In the preparation of each Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning event, a clear topic was defined for each event, to be analysed during the event with the contribution of all event participants.

TIME4CS works on the complex matter of Institutional Changes to promote public engagement and Citizen Science in Research Performing Organizations. Such complex matter comprises several areas of discussion (potential topics) and could be tackled with a broader approach or with a more targeted approach, through the involvement of specific actors of the quadruple helix to discuss specific progress and to ensure the achievement of sustainable Institutional Changes. In particular, TIME4CS works on 4 specific Intervention Areas - 1) *Research*, 2) *Education and Awareness*, 3) *Support resources and Infrastructure*, and 4) *Policy and Assessment* – and events could be organized focusing on one of these areas, to ensure more specificity and a more thorough understanding of the topic analysed.

Moreover, during the implementation phase of the project, events on specific Grounding Actions were organized to further discuss concrete actions and potential barriers and challenges to tackle and to maximize the benefits of the interaction between Front-Runners and Implementers.

Finally, in the case of co-creation and co-designing events, Implementers were encouraged to keep a balance between keeping the topic broad enough to benefit from the contribution of different actors, and at the same time narrow enough to ensure that the interaction led to concrete outputs (e.g. actions to include in the roadmaps, such as in the 1st co-creation meeting). Especially in the case of these events, as participants were attending on a voluntarily basis, it was crucial that the topic was relevant for them and that they could see the importance of their contribution to the project's activities in a friendly and positive environment.

3.2.3 Selection of participants

For each of the three types of Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events, TIME4CS had the possibility to invite participants beyond the project team already involved. Due to the nature of the project, which concerns Institutional Changes in Research Performing Organizations, a collaboration between different groups, i.e. researchers, support staff and governance members within each partner's organization was sought.

Depending on the overall aim of the event organized, the expected outputs and outcomes, and the local context, the organizing partner was responsible for deciding who to invite to the different events to ensure the most productive environment. It was also important to keep in mind an appropriate number of participants. A large number of participants may not always be the right choice, especially for events where concrete actions had to be defined. At the same time, it was important to keep a balanced representation

across the participants (e.g. types of quadruple helix actors, gender, etc.), unless the specific topic of the event was clearly of more interest to a specific category of stakeholders.

In reaching out to participants, it was recommended to consider the best way to approach them and to provide them, in due time, with all the relevant information about their expected contribution and benefits they could gain from the event. An adequate preparation of the participants was considered one of the success factors of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events.

3.2.4 Define the activities

Once the outputs, outcomes, topic and participants had been defined, the activities to be carried out during the event were prepared. It is worth to point out that the first versions of this document did not aim at providing a list of methods and activities, given the broad availability of engagement methods online resources^{11,12,13} and since the TIME4CS consortium can benefit from the support and expertise of several partners with a high level of experience in the design of events to stimulate dialogue and involve different actors.

The partner responsible for organizing the event was encouraged to benefit from such consortium expertise, e.g. by circulating among the partners a short concept note of the event with clear definitions of expected outputs and outcomes, topic and participants, for example by using the format of the reporting template (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT EVENT REPORT).

Next step was to select a date and time for the event that took into account the availability of participants and the preparation time needed. This included the choice of an appropriate length for the event (which would differ between in person and online events), which must ensure the achievement of the event's objectives and at the same time take into account the commitment required, especially from stakeholders external to the project's activities.

Finally, it was important to choose a proper location. In the case of face-to-face events, one must take into consideration the space necessary for the chosen activities. In case of online events, one may consider the online tools available (e.g. MIRO) and how they match with the needs for the activities and expected results.

3.2.5 Assess the outputs and outcomes

After each activity, the organizers were required to complete a report describing the details of their activities and writing down the main findings. The report, for which a template is provided (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT EVENT REPORT), included an assessment of the outputs of the events, expected outcomes and an evaluation with a focus on lessons learnt (both in terms of success factors and difficulties encountered) as reported in D5.3 Final Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report¹⁴.

¹¹ <https://siscodeproject.eu/>

¹² <http://engage2020.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/projects/sparks>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486205>

4. Schedule of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events

In the following table (Table 1), the final schedule of the TIME4CS Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events is reported.

Table 1 - TIME4CS Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events (chronological order)

Title of the event	Time	Organizer	Task	Phase of TIME4CS methodology
Workshop Frontrunners	13th April 2021	UZH	T1.2	Consolidation of Knowledge
1st learning visit (Education and Awareness)	19th October 2021	AU	T3.2	Consolidation of Knowledge; Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
2nd learning visit (Research)	27th October 2021	UCL	T3.2	Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps; Consolidation of Knowledge
3 rd learning visit (Support and Infrastructure & Policy and Assessment)	3rd November 2021	UZH	T3.2	Consolidation of Knowledge; Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
1st Co-Creation meeting - KTU	20/10/2021	KTU	T2.2	Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
1st Co-Creation meeting - UniSR	25/10/2021	UniSR	T2.2	Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
1 st Co-Creation meeting - T-UCC	28 October 2021	T-UCC	T2.2	Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
1st Co-Creation meeting - CRG	3 November 2021	CRG	T2.2	Co-Design of Implementers Roadmaps
1st Implementers Forum	26th April 2022	APRE	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
1st Implementers Journey - UNISR	30th June 2022	UniSR	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
1st Implementers Journey - KTU	4th July 2022	KTU	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
1st Implementers Journey - CRG	16th June 2022	CRG	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
1st Implementers Journey - T-UCC	13th July 2022	T-UCC	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
Mentoring Visit-CRG	9th May 2023	CRG	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
Mentoring Visit-UniSR	18th May 2023	UniSR	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes

Title of the event	Time	Organizer	Task	Phase of TIME4CS methodology
Mentoring Visit - T-UCC	27th March 2023	T-UCC	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
Mentoring Visit - KTU	14th March 2023	KTU	T.3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
2nd Co-Creation Meeting - CRG	17th November 2022	CRG	T2.2	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes; Evaluation and Impact Assessment
2nd Co-Creation Meeting - UniSR	11th November 2022	UniSR	T2.2	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes; Evaluation and Impact Assessment
2nd Co-Creation Meeting - T-UCC	25th March 2022	T-UCC	T2.2	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes; Evaluation and Impact Assessment
2nd Co-Creation Meeting 2 - KTU	28th November 2022	KTU	T2.2	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes; Evaluation and Impact Assessment
2nd Implementers Forum	18th November 2022	APRE	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
2nd Implementers Journey - UniSR	14th December 2022	UniSR	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
2nd Implementers Journey - KTU	14th December 2022	KTU	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
2nd Implementers Journey - CRG	14th December 2022	CRG	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
2nd Implementers Journey - T-UCC	14th December 2022	T-UCC	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes
3rd Implementers Forum	27th June 2023	APRE	T3.3	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Co-Creation Meeting - CRG	23rd October 2023	CRG	T2.2	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Co-Creation Meeting 3 - UniSR	22nd November 2023	UniSR	T2.2	Evaluation and Impact Assessment

Title of the event	Time	Organizer	Task	Phase of TIME4CS methodology
3rd Co-Creation Meeting - T-UCC	25th October 2023	T-UCC	T2.2	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Co-Creation Meeting 3 - KTU	21st November 2023	KTU	T2.2	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Implementers Journey - UniSR	4th October 2023	UniSR	T3.3	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Implementers Journey - KTU	16th October 2023	KTU	T3.3	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Implementers Journey - CRG	18th October 2023	CRG	T3.3	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
3rd Implementers Journey - T-UCC	9th November 2023	T-UCC	T3.3	Evaluation and Impact Assessment
4th Implementers Forum	2nd November 2023	APRE	T3.3	Implementation of Actions leading to Institutional Changes

5. Conclusions

This plan for the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events was primarily written for TIME4CS partners to be used as a guide in the organization of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning events, through the definition of a **common framework** that specifies the objectives of the different types of events and provides concrete guidelines in the design and organization of events. It is important to underline that this common framework, as described in the first version of the document, was paramount for the design of effective learning activities that could support the implementation of TIME4CS activities as foreseen in other WPs. Therefore, TIME4CS partners actively used and referred to the document as a reference guide in the preparation of events.

This document represents the updated version of the plan, after the implementation of all foreseen events, and therefore, although it keeps the overview of the guidelines as preparation for partners of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events, it also provides an overview of the events carried out. All planned events were carried out, and they were adapted to the needs of Implementers. In particular, all the events carried out in the last six months of the project (from June 2023 onward) were focusing on evaluation and impact assessment of the activities carried out. Namely, the 3rd Implementers Forum (June 2023) was a sustainability workshop, while both the co-creation meetings and Implementers Journeys were focusing on discussing the impact of the project activities on the implementing institutions to evaluate how all actions were leading to sustainable long term institutional changes. These aspects are reported in D5.3 Final Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report¹⁵.

Overall, the mutual learning activities have proven very effective in supporting the Implementers in the long process of carrying out actions leading to institutional changes to promote Citizen Science as research methodology within their institutions. Each organization had different needs and different institutional frameworks that were taken into account. They could benefit from the exchange and mentoring support of Front-Runners, but also from the exchange among themselves focusing on common challenges faced in the implementation of their Grounding Actions and discussing possible solutions to overcome them, based on the common experience they were going through as part of the TIME4CS project. The mutual learning activities also benefitted the Front-Runners, as they gained insights into other institutions' challenges and opportunities with embedding Citizen Science in their practice. Front-Runners also gained insights on their own organisations, as they reflected on their own citizen science-related practices. And finally, through participating in the mutual learning events, the Front-Runners also realized that each institution is different and thus, the path and Grounding Actions leading to the institutional changes needed to support Citizen Science, are dependent on each institutional context.

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486205>

6. References

Anne-Charlotte Hoes, Greet Overbeek, Susanna Albertini and Carlijn Savelkouls Guide for Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops, BIOVOICES

<https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=39&l=en&key=7d8bc103e1b7d3bc1748c5a29c052074>

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Luisa Barbosa, & Gema Revuelta. (2019). Guide: How to organize Mobilization and Mutual Learning Processes - Public Engagement in Science. GRECO project <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2652776>

APPENDIX A – DRAFT EVENT REPORT

Event name

Date

Name of the organization in charge of the event

Event Report

General Information

Venue	
Date	
Organizer	
Length	
Total number of participants	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

List of Participants

Please include the list of participants

Name	Organization	Role

Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer.

Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event	
Output(s)	
Expected outcome(s)	
Topic	
Type of participants (e.g. Academia, Research Funding Organizations, Policy-Makers, Civil Society, Business, Citizen Science initiatives, others to specify)	
Activities performed	

Lessons learnt

Please briefly describe main successes and difficulties related to this specific event, if any. Please provide suggestions for similar or future events (including improvements you would like to apply in the next events you will organize).

APPENDIX B – Implementers Journey Review

Implementers’ Journey Review

This document is a tool for the Implementers to follow, share, and document their process of working with Grounding Actions (GAs). It will secure a consistent structure for the Implementers’ Journey Review (IJR) and assure the minutes taking, helping both Front-runners and Implementers to prepare for future meetings and follow up on the monitoring and mentoring efforts.

This template proposes a generic agenda with questions that can guide the conversations at the meetings. On page two, there is a general meeting information and an overview of the status of the Grounding Actions. On page three and onward, there are tables for each GA and a place for taking notes that will complete the minutes.

The **Implementers will fill in in this template and send it to all participants prior to each meeting**. After each IJR, the whole form is finalized and uploaded to the dedicated folder ([here](#)) no later than one week after the meeting.

Agenda for each relevant GA:

1. What activities have you been working on since last IJR and how?
2. Which were the positive outcomes of these activities? What worked out well and what were the benefits?
3. Have you experienced any challenges/obstacles? How have you (tried to) overcome them?
4. Have you experienced any unintended consequences? If yes, which ones?
5. What are the next planned activities?
6. Are you anticipating any risks and what is your strategy to mitigate them?

How can the Implementers help you, do you need any resources?

General meeting information

Implementer:	Choose an item.		
DATE:	Click or tap to enter a date.	TIME:	Click or tap here to enter text.
MEETING MODERATOR:	Click or tap here to enter text.	RAPPORTEURS:	Click or tap here to enter text.
FRONT RUNNERS AND/OR OTHER PARTICIPANTS:	Click or tap here to enter text.		

Overview of the Grounding Actions:

GA TITLE	INTERVENTION AREA	STATUS
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item
Click or tap here to enter text.	Choose an item.	Choose an item

GA1: Click or tap here to enter text.	
	Activity (as presented in D2.1) Steps taken towards activity completion
Work done since last meeting:	
Positive outcomes:	
Experienced challenges:	
Unintended consequences:	
	Activity (as presented in D2.1) Steps to be taken towards activity completion

Work to be done next:		
Anticipated risks:	Description	Mitigation strategy
Needed help and resources:		
Other comments:		

GA2: Click or tap here to enter text.		
	Activity (as presented in D2.1)	Steps taken towards activity completion
Work done since last meeting:		
Positive outcomes:		
Experienced challenges:		
Unintended consequences:		
	Activity (as presented in D2.1)	Steps to be taken towards activity completion

Work to be done next:		
Anticipated risks:	Description	Mitigation strategy
Needed help and resources:		
Other comments:		

Minutes:

